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Urban Freight: What about construction logistics?

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Agenda

- Introduction
- Methodology
- Comparative analysis and results
- Conclusions

08.05.2018

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 633338.

Introduction

- UFT plays an essential role in the functioning of cities
- Need for new and renovated constructions is growing
- Building materials can make up to 30% of tons carried across cities
- But attention for construction supply chain quite limited
- The construction sector suffers from a poor productivity performance

What are the specific characteristics of the construction supply chain when compared to more frequently studied urban supply chains?

Introduction

SUCCESS Id Card

- **SUCCESS:** Sustainable Urban Consolidation CentrES for conStruction
- **Thematic area:** Reduction of costs and negative impacts of the construction supply chain
- **Topic:** To what extent and how can the supply chain management and Construction Consolidation Centres (CCCs) concepts bring about generic solutions to improve the construction supply chains?
- **Duration:** 36 months (Start 01/05/2015)
- **Total budget:** 3.2 M €
- **Funding:** European Commission, Horizon 2020 programme, MG-5.2-2014: Reducing impacts & costs of freight & service trips in urban areas
- **CIVITAS:** SUCCESS is one of the H2020 projects that have been selected to become member of the network

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Methodology

- Literature review (Bestufs, Freturb...)
- Quantitative analysis : UFT surveys of logistics operations in 4 construction sites
 - Daily observation over 8 months
 - 4,436 deliveries and pickups trips manually recorded

Address of the loading location
Address of the previous delivery 2
Address of the previous delivery 1
Address of next delivery 1
Address of next delivery 2
Address of final come back
Starting time from the loading location (time)
Arrival time in urban area (time)
Arrival time near the construction site (time)
Planned delivery time 1 (time)
Planned delivery time 2 (time)
Arrival time at construction site (time)
Starting time of unloading (time)
Ending time of unloading (time)
Material weight (kg)
Roundtrip or Direct trip (choice list)
Come back empty or loaded (choice list)
Vehicle Euroclass (choice list)
Vehicle Fuel type (choice list)
Gross vehicle weight rating (GVWR) (kg)
Vehicle Net weight (kg)
Vehicle surface (sqm)
Vehicle type (choice list)

Methodology

Pilot sites

Luxembourg (Luxembourg)

- 11,400 m²
- 21 M€
- Refurbishment & construction of apartments, shops, offices

Paris (France)

- 55,475 m²
- 230 M€
- Conversion of two buildings into a single complex with offices

Valencia (Spain)

- 7,772 m²
- 16 M€
- Renovation of historic buildings and construction of new ones

Verona (Italy)

- 83,914 m²
- 126 M€
- Enlargement and renovation of two hospitals

Comparative analysis and result

General

- UFT is complex, diverse and fragmented
- 2 UFT functional classes:
 - Consumer-related distribution (retail, food, home deliveries)
 - Producer-related distribution (construction materials, waste and industrial goods)
- Construction sector shares similarities with both industry and services sectors

Characteristic	Commonly known urban supply chains	Construction supply chains
Supply chain	“Permanent”	Temporary

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Comparative analysis

Stakeholders in the construction supply chain

- Consumers (contractors)
 - Temporary multi-organization
 - Long-term partnership difficult because of the SC temporariness and tendering procedures
 - Address issues : location change frequently, sometimes don't exist, access path, difficult to find person in charge of validations a delivery
- Main contractor : additional actor in the SC
 - Limited vision of the SC but has a direct impact on delivery schedule
- Shippers (suppliers)
 - Many suppliers which vary along the project and between projects
- Freight carriers
 - Mainly own-account transport
 - Trip length varies a lot (from 66 to 350 km on average in Success)

Results

Stakeholders

Characteristic	Commonly known urban supply chains	Construction supply chains
Consumers	Residents Fixed delivery address	Contractors Temporary delivery address
Shippers	Manufacturers, wholesalers, retailers	Manufacturers, wholesalers
Freight carriers	Own-account/Third party Short trip length	Own-account Medium trip length

Fragmentation of the construction is the main barrier against a more sustainable UFT

Comparative analysis

Vehicles in the construction sector

- Large variety of trucks, mainly HGVs
- Trucks specific to the sector

Dump truck

Source: Tralux, Luxembourg

Truck mixer

Source: Béton Feidt, Luxembourg

Truck with on-board crane

Source: Glaserner-Betz, Luxembourg

Side curtains

Construction truck

Source: Luxembourg

Results

Vehicles

Characteristic	Commonly known urban supply chains	Construction supply chains
Vehicle size	LGV <i>71% in Mexico, 61% in Paris</i>	HGV <i>95 – 100% in 3 out of 4 sites, 2/3 deliveries in the last one</i>
Access to the vehicle load	Rear and side	Side (curtains) and top

The vehicle size currently used is an opportunity for consolidating and reducing the environmental impact of the UFT.

But, consolidation with other supply chains seems difficult.

Comparative analysis

Deliveries in the construction sector

- Long waiting time

Booking request
Source: Vinci, Paris

	Average truck waiting time
Luxembourg	00:24
Paris	00:36
Valencia	00:18
Verona	00:35

Waiting time (inside and outside the site)
Source: SUCCES

Entrance gate and access to the site
Source: CMB, Verona

Results

Delivery

Characteristic	Commonly known urban supply chains	Construction supply chains
Organisational mode	Multi-drop round	Single-drop trip
Delivery scheduling	Moderate use, both fixed time and time window	Highly used, mostly fixed time window
Delivery time	Mainly during the morning (6-12 AM)	
Duration of stops	Short stop duration (around 15 min)	Long stop duration (around 45 min)
Delivery frequency	3 to 10 deliveries per week	12.5 to 50 deliveries per week
Operation type	2 deliveries for 1 pickup	
Delivery point / Storage	Fixed storage capacity	scalable, temporary and moveable storage capacity

The fragmentation of the construction sector is again a barrier to consolidation opportunities. The lack of coordination, communication and information and communication technologies (ICT) explains also the poor performance of sector's deliveries.

Comparative analysis

Building material in the construction sector

- 48% pallets, 14% boxes, 7% racks (source : SUCCESS)
- Unloading with equipment available on site (crane, forklift, truck with on-board crane...)
- Limited space for storage
- Up to 30% of tonnage carried in cities (source : L. Dablanc)

Palletized building material

Source: Vinci, Paris

Waste sorting

Source: Tralux, Luxembourg

Material handling with a crane

Source: CMB, Verona

Results

Material

Characteristic	Commonly known urban supply chains	Construction supply chains
Unit load	Boxes	Pallets
Goods handling	By hand (or trolley)	By crane or forklift
Material storage	Fixed, indoor	Moving, indoor or outdoor
Weight/Volume	Highly variable	8.2 to 10.2 tons per day
Volume variability	Due to seasonality	Due to regulation and weather conditions

There is a clear opportunity to consolidate building materials since most of them are robust products at relatively low cost and with a long lifespan.

Comparative analysis

UFT policy measures

- Low consideration of UFT in the urban planning process
- UFT policies less restrictive for construction SC
 - Permits accorded to construction vehicles to enter regulated zones
 - Loading bays do not fit the needs in construction
 - UCC vs CCC

Operations at a Construction Consolidation Centre

Source: Transport for London, directory of CCCs

Loading of a dump truck
Source: Tralux, Luxembourg

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Results

UFT policy measures

Characteristic	Commonly known urban supply chains	Construction supply chains
Urban planning	Low consideration of UFT in the urban planning process	
UFT policies	Exemptions for construction	
Loading areas	Fixed public space provided by cities	Public space temporary rented by main contractor

Public sector which accounts for a third of the total construction spending in America and Europe is paramount to improve the situation

Conclusions

○ Construction supply chains

- Literature review confirms that few researches are carried on CSC in urban areas
- Significant differences in the logistics patterns
- Solutions investigated for common SC not applicable directly to CSC
- Unique and understudied

○ Potential optimization strategies

- Construction Consolidation Centre
- ICT (RFID)
- Off-peak deliveries

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